

KEY INDICATORS

With 309,487 ha, Finland has 13.6% of its farmland under organic management, thus above the EU average of 11.1%. Organic farmland more than doubled from 2001 to 2024, growing slightly slower than in the European Union. Regarding organic retail sales, a turnover of 335 million euros was achieved, constituting 1.8% of all organic food retail sales in Finland.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)	147,943 ha (6.7%)	309,487 ha (13.6%)
Area Growth from 2001 to 2024	109.2%	

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)	73,750 ha (3.4%)	274,574 ha (12.2%)
Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)	707 ha (19.6%)	861 ha (23.2%)
Grassland* (Share of Total)	4 ha	N/D
Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)	N/D	N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)	4,983 (6.5%)	4,058 (8.9%)
Aquaculture Producers	N/D	N/D
Processors	448	379
Importers	9	45

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)	N/D	335 M€ (1.8%)
Per Capita Consumption	N/D	59.6 €
Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024	N/D	
Imports	N/D	11,460 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

ORGANIC FARMLAND GROWTH IN FINLAND

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on Pro Luomu, Elvira, Eurostat and Nic Lampkin

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES GROWTH IN FINLAND

Source: Pro Luomu

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Finland CAP strategic plan sets out a doubling of the organic area by 2027 compared with 2018, to reach 25% of total UAA. This is to be achieved with a 50% increase in annual expenditure. Total annual expenditure will only increase by 60%, implying a fall of 24% in average expenditure per ha. As payments per ha for specific land uses have increased, this implies a proportionately greater growth in arable land area. Payments for conversion at the same rates as maintenance are set to continue in 2023-2027. The introduction of a 30% saleable crops area requirement in 2023 for farms with conventional livestock resulted in a reduction of total organic land area as some of these farms decertified.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	274 kha	580 kha (+112%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	12.1%	25.6% (+112%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	92%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	56 M€	90 M€ (+60%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	205 €	155 € (-24%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	385 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	430 M€	17.6%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	1,762 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	6,657 M€	5.8%

*Including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS**	HORTICULTURE**	FRUIT CROPS**	LIVESTOCK*
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	160	160	590	590	130
	2026	P2	184	184	679	679	150
Change from 2023 to 2026			+15%	+15%	+15%	+15%	+15%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	160	160	590	590	130
	2026	P2	184	184	679	679	150
Change from 2023 to 2026			+15%	+15%	+15%	+15%	+15%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2023		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2026		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

*2LU required per ha grass/arable land paid, effectively 65/75 €/LU

** Saleable crops area (excl. grass) must be >30% of organic area for farms with conventional livestock

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Finland is on its second national organic action plan, the first starting in 2013. The current action plan represents a development of more detailed actions, especially relating to information. The increases in targets for land area and public procurement are more modest, reflecting shortfalls in target outcomes in 2020. The action plan has no specific funding, but other programmes can be used. Stakeholders play a key role in implementation. The plan builds on increasing knowledge in the organic value chain.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET*	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2013-20	20% of UAA by 2020	3x 2012 market share / 20% of public catering
Current Action Plan	2022-30	25% of UAA by 2030	5% market share by 2030 / 25% of public catering

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2013 - 2020)

10% annual growth, especially livestock, horticulture; investment aid for manure, slurry storage

Support for producer organisations; simplification of regulations for small businesses; increased product range; stronger supply chain networks; inclusion in public catering with information, also in tourism; development of export strategy; adaptation of control systems

Production focus, rapid dissemination of research results; develop training and CPD provision; encourage use of EU funds for research and innovation; increase availability of certification and market data

PRODUCTION

MARKETS

INFORMATION

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2022 - 2030)

Increase production to meet demand, including livestock, horticulture, bees

Support for producer groups, regional strategies, short supply chains, exports; regional targets for public catering, development of tourism, hospitality catering with certification system; export support focus on wild berries, aquaculture; assess logos and branding experience in other countries; international comparisons to develop control system

Information campaign to stimulate consumer demand, label recognition, regulation awareness, confidence in benefits; high quality advice for all actors; develop training and education, closer collaboration between institutions and sector at all levels; implement organic research strategy; assess market data needs and opportunities

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Finland is negligible. Finland was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. The current national organic action plan commits to exploring aquaculture opportunities, but has no specific initiatives. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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